

Disclaimer

The NEMECYS project is co-funded by the European Union under grant agreement ID 101094323, by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee grant numbers 10065802, 10050933 and 10061304, and by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

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Network Assessment Tool user guide

Network Assessment Tool is a comprehensive tool designed to assess network environments with various devices, including medical IoT devices, laptops, smartphones, and more. It efficiently discovers devices connected to the network and gathers critical data for each device, such as operating system details, open ports, running services, and any relevant CVEs associated with these services. Additionally, NTTool leverages a mirrored port or MITM to capture traffic samples and analyze them for potential malicious indicators in the network's traffic exchange. All collected information is compiled into a user-friendly PDF report. Aside that all outcomes can be easily shared with other tools for further analysis or risk assessment via json scheme exports.

The tool will identify all active devices on the network and perform port scanning on each one detected. It will then fingerprint each device to determine the operating system, running services, and known vulnerabilities. Network traffic samples are obtained from each detected device using a MITM (Man-in-the-Middle) technique, or via a mirror port in as an alternative. Traffic will be captured over a specific period, recording details like destination IPs and request types. Destination IPs will be checked against blacklist databases, and metadata will be gathered for each. Additionally, payloads will be inspected for any malicious content. Finally, a comprehensive report will summarize these findings, providing detailed insights into device activity and potential risks.

Through network assessment, the tool is capable identify outdated devices on the network that pose significant risks due to outdated or unsupported software, as well as devices with reported active exploits that may be unknown to the infrastructure owner. Additionally, it generates a network "map" to help locate hidden devices that could be malicious or unauthorized to connect to the network.

Usage Instructions

The tool is available for download at the provided URL. It is a standalone executable and does not require installation. Additionally, the tool supports a Dockerized environment, eliminating the need to install additional packages required for assessments.

The tool is designed to run on Ubuntu Linux systems but can also be used on Windows via a containerized environment (using WSL). For Windows setups, ensure that the network interfaces are visible to the WSL system for proper operation.

Videos have been recorded to guide users through the processes, providing step-by-step instructions to help them effectively utilize the tool. These videos serve as a

practical resource, ensuring clarity and enhancing understanding of each function and feature, making the tool more accessible and user-friendly. Videos are available [here](#)

Use tool with docker environment (Preferrable way)

The tool is designed to perform network assessments seamlessly using a Docker instance. This eliminates the need to install additional packages or dependencies on the host environment, making it more convenient to use. By leveraging Docker, the tool ensures a streamlined setup process and avoids cluttering the environment with unnecessary components that typical users may not require.

The only prerequisite for using the tool is having Docker installed on your computer. To simplify the process, installation and uninstallation scripts are included, ensuring a hassle-free setup and removal experience.

In the `nat_tool` root folder, you will find two scripts: `prepare_environment.sh` and `clean_environment.sh`. These scripts are designed to help with installation and configuration tasks. **Install docker and configuration:**

```
chmod +x ./prepare_environment.sh
sudo ./prepare_environment.sh --interface=<interface_name> #Optional
```

The NAT tool uses the network of a specified interface to perform assessments. If there are multiple network interfaces and the scan needs to target a specific one (rather than the default or main interface), you must specify it using the interface argument. If it is not specified then it will use the main by default.

After the script executes successfully, you can verify that Docker has been installed correctly by running the following command

```
sudo docker version
```

Now that Docker is available, the tool is ready to run. In the `real_environment` folder, there are four files, but for now, our focus is on the script named `init_scan_dockerized.sh`. This script is used to initiate the tool and begin the network assessment process in a Dockerized environment by simplifying the process.

The network assessment tool supports several optional arguments that can be specified directly in the command line to configure the assessment according to your needs. Below is an explanation of these optional arguments:

Argument	Description	Default Value
interface	Specifies the network interface to be used for the assessment. Use this when the scan targets a specific interface instead of the default one.	Default Inteface
packet_scan	Enable or disable network packet capture for each device on the network for a specified time period. Setting the value to true enables packet capture, while false disables it.	false

tcp_scan	Configure the type of port scanning to be performed. Setting the value to top scans a predefined list of commonly used ports, while setting it to all scans the entire range of ports.	top
udp_scan	Configure the type of port scanning to be performed. Setting the value to top scans a predefined list of commonly used ports, while setting it to all scans the entire range of ports.	top
capture_duration	Specify the time period for capturing network data for assessment. The duration should be provided as an integer value representing seconds.	60
capture_type	Specify method for capturing network data. Setting the value to mitm for mitm method, while setting value to mirror will make use of mirror interface	mirror
mirror_interface	Specify the name of mirror interface	None

Note: The default capture method is set to "Mirror." Mirror interfaces replicate the entire network traffic, providing a safer and more comprehensive way to capture and analyze data. However, they require configuration by a network administrator. Alternatively, a "mitm" (Man-in-the-Middle) method is also available for capturing traffic, eliminating the need for a mirror port. While this approach can simplify setup, it may introduce disruptions to the network. **To run the script use the following command:**

```
chmod +x ./init_scan_dockerized.sh
sudo ./init_scan_dockerized --interface=<interface_name> --packet_scan=<true|false> -
udp_scan=<all|top> --capture_duration=<seconds>
```

Use tool without docker environment

To use the NAT tool, ensure the following packages are installed, along with their respective functionalities:

- **python3:** The main Python interpreter required to run the tool. **python3-pip:** A package manager for installing Python libraries. **nmap:** A application used for discovering ports. **iptables:** A utility for managing network packet filtering and NAT rules. **net-tools:** A collection of networking utilities (e.g., ifconfig, netstat). **iputils-ping:** A utility for testing network connectivity via ICMP ping. **iproute2:** A suite of tools for network configuration and routing.

Run the script `install_dependencies.sh` to automatically install these dependencies and set up the tool for proper operation.

```
chmod +x ./install_dependencies.sh
sudo install_dependencies.sh
```

Once the script executes successfully, the NAT tool is ready to use.

The network assessment tool supports several optional arguments that can be specified directly in the command line to configure the assessment according to your needs. Below is an explanation of these optional arguments:

Argument	Description	Default Value
interface	Specifies the network interface to be used for the assessment. Use this when the scan targets a specific interface instead of the default one.	Default Interface
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tcp_scan	Configure the type of port scanning to be performed. Setting the value to top scans a predefined list of commonly used ports, while setting it to all scans the entire range of ports.	top
udp_scan	Configure the type of port scanning to be performed. Setting the value to top scans a predefined list of commonly used ports, while setting it to all scans the entire range of ports.	top
capture_duration	Specify the time period for capturing network data for assessment. The duration should be provided as an integer value representing seconds.	60
capture_type	Specify method for capturing network data. Setting the value to mitm for mitm method, while setting value to mirror will make use of mirror interface	mirror
mirror_interface	Specify the name of mirror interface	None

Note: The default capture method is set to "Mirror." Mirror interfaces replicate the entire network traffic, providing a safer and more comprehensive way to capture and analyze data. However, they require configuration by a network administrator. Alternatively, a "mitm" (Man-in-the-Middle) method is also available for capturing traffic, eliminating the need for a mirror port. While this approach can simplify setup, it may introduce disruptions to the network. To run the tool, execute the following command:

```
sudo ./ntt.bin # args
```

Please note: A cleanup script has been provided to remove all dependencies installed for the tool. However, **be cautious when running this script, as it will remove all the dependencies listed earlier**, including any that may have existed on your system prior to using the tool.

```
chmod +x ./clean_environment
sudo ./clean_environment.sh
```

Test tool in virtual environment

To facilitate testing of the tool and verify outcomes without impacting a real environment, a script has been included to create and assess a virtual testing environment. This script leverages containers to simulate a virtual network and it is located on `virtual_environment` folder .

The predefined scenario features a network comprising five devices, each representing common vulnerabilities often found in IoT devices, including medical devices that are outdated or no longer supported. The scenario includes:

- A device running an outdated version of Apache, reflecting a common vulnerability in legacy IoT devices.
- A device running an outdated version of Nginx, another typical issue with unsupported IoT systems. A device running an outdated version of a generic web server, illustrating the prevalence of obsolete software in connected devices. A device running an outdated version of SSH, highlighting the risks associated with unpatched communication protocols in IoT. A device generating malicious requests to simulate potential threat activity. A device producing network traffic from blacklisted IPs (using a dummy blacklist for demonstration purposes).

This virtual scenario can be extended by modifying the `scan_vuln_containers.sh` script. Users can add additional containers representing services present in their network, enabling customized vulnerability assessments tailored to specific environments.

After the virtual scenario ends, all containers used for the assessment will be cleaned up automatically, ensuring no remnants of the test environment remain. The generated reports will be available in the `report` folder for review.

To execute virtual scenario use following commands

```
chmod +x ./init_scan_dockerized.sh
sudo ./init_scan_dockerized.sh
```